

Infrared Absorption Spectra of Some Dibromoanilines

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Infrared absorption spectra of 2,4-, 2,5- and 2,6-dibromoanilines have been recorded in the region 250–4000 cm^{-1} using KBr pellet technique. The observed frequencies have been assigned to the different modes of vibration assuming C_s symmetry for 2,4- and 2,5-dibromoanilines and C_{2v} symmetry for 2,6-dibromoaniline.

The infrared absorption spectra of some chloro, fluoro and bromoanilines and a few di-derivatives of fluoro and chloroanilines^{1,2,3} have been recently reported from this laboratory and elsewhere. In continuation of these studies, the infrared absorption spectra of 2,4-, 2,5- and 2,6-dibromoanilines have now been studied on which on earlier work was available. The observed bands have been assigned to the different modes of vibrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples were obtained from Koch-Light Laboratories, U.K. of L.R. grade quality and were used after recrystallization. The infrared traces of all these compounds were taken on a Perkin Elmer 521 grating spectrophotometer in the range 250–4000 cm^{-1} . The compounds were made into pellets mixed with KBr powder. The observed fundamental vibrational frequencies and their proposed assignments are given in Table I.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It has been found that the vibrational spectra of several substituted benzenes can be well interpreted by regarding the substituent group as a mass point. This simplified model of the molecule has only 30 normal modes of vibration, the other fundamental vibrations of the molecule are treated as group vibrations. Under this simplifying assumption the molecules 2,4- and 2,5-dibromoanilines belong to point-group C_s whereas 2,6-dibromoaniline would belong to C_{2v} point group. The 30 normal modes of vibration of the molecules can then be divided as $21a'$ (planar) and $9a''$ (non-planar) in C_s point group and as $11a_1+10b_1$ (planar) and $3a_2+6b_2$ (non-planar) in C_{2v} point group. All the vibrations except the a_2 vibrations of C_{2v} point group are allowed in infrared spectrum. In addition to these vibrations, six internal vibrations of the amine group would also be observed.

C-H vibrations : The C–H stretching vibrations of the benzene derivatives are observed in the region 3000–3100 cm^{-1} . Three such vibrations are expected to be observed in the compounds under discussion as there are three C–H bonds. The identification of these

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vibrations is complicated due to the presence of N-H frequencies in this range and lack of resolution. The frequencies 3038, 3055 cm^{-1} in 2,4-dibromoaniline and 3040, 3085 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoaniline are assigned to this mode of vibration. However, in the case of 2,5-dibromoaniline only one frequency at 3065 cm^{-1} could be observed.

TABLE I

Fundamental vibrational frequencies and their assignments of 2,4-; 2,5- and 2,6-dibromoanilines

2,4-dibromo- aniline (cm^{-1})	2,5-dibromo- aniline (cm^{-1})	2,6-dibromo- aniline (cm^{-1})	Species		Assignments
			C_s	C_{2v}	
299 (1)	290 (1)	299 (1)	a'	a_1	C-Br i.p. bending
320 (1)	316 (1)	312 (1)	a'	a_1	C-Br i.p. bending
390 (5)	391 (2)	385 (1)	a'	b_2	C-C o.p. ring def.
422 (5)	424 (sh)	438 (2)	a'	a_1	C-C i.p. bending
528 (8)	551 (3)	542 (sh)	a'	b_1	C-C i.p. bending
618 (9)	626 (6)	620 (6)	a'	a_1	C-Br stretching
665 (7)	655 (6)	666 (2)	a'	a_1	C-Br stretching
700 (6)	701 (3)	704 (10)	a'	b_1	NH ₂ wagging
805 (10)	783 (9)	748 (10)	a''	b_2	C-H o.p. bending
830 (7)	838 (9)	829 (2)	a'	a_1	C-C ring breathing
860 (7)	890 (2)	899 (3)	a''	b_2	C-H o.p. bending
930 (3)	937 (1)	940 (4)	a''	b_2	"
1025 (6)	1026 (10)	1025 (6)	a'	a_1	C-C-C trigonal bending
1063 (3)	1063 (3)	1045 (9)	a''	b_2	N-H twisting
1089 (1)	1109 (sh)	1092 (1)	a'	a_1	C-H i.p. bending
1141 (3)	1149 (3)	1150 (sh)	a'	b_1	"
1242 (4)	1240 (sh)	1225 (2)	a'	b_1	"
1275 (6)	1260 (5)	1289 (6)	a'	a_1	C-NH ₂ stretching
1300 (1)	1302 (3)	1312 (sh)	a'	b_1	C-C stretching
1450 (7)	1460 (sh)	1437 (10)	a'	a_1	"
1502 (1)	1515 (1)	1512 (1)	a'	b_1	"
1548 (2)	1543 (1)	1535 (2)	a'	a_1	"
1570 (1)	1575 (3)	1568 (1)	a'	b_1	"
1600 (6)	1620 (9)	1597 (10)	a'	b_1	N-H i.p. bending
3038 (2)	—	3040 (1)	a'	a_1	C-H stretching
3055 (2)	3065 (1)	3085 (1)	a'	a_1	"
3282 (3)	3260 (4)	3280 (6)			Combination
3380 (3)	3378 (2)	3370 (4)	a'	a_1	N-H sym. stretching
3470 (2)	3480 (2)	3465 (2)	a'	b_1	N-H asym. stretching

N.B. : The corresponding intensity is given in the parentheses.

i.p. = in-plane; o.p. = out-of-plane; def. = deformation; sym. = symmetric; asym. = asymmetric and sh = shoulder.

The C-H bending modes in substituted benzenes occur in two different frequency range 1000–1300 cm^{-1} (in-plane bending modes) and 750–1000 cm^{-1} (out-of-plane bending modes). We have assigned the frequencies observed at 1089, 1141 and 1242 cm^{-1} in 2,4-dibromoaniline, at 1109, 1149 and 1240 cm^{-1} in 2,5-dibromoaniline and at 1092, 1150 and

1225 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoaniline to the C-H in plane bending modes. Similarly the frequencies at 805, 860 and 930 cm^{-1} in 2,4-dibromoaniline, at 783, 890 and 937 cm^{-1} in 2,5-dibromoaniline and at 748, 899 and 940 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoaniline are assigned to the C-H out of plane bending modes of vibration.

Ring Vibrations : The four carbon stretching modes of benzene namely e_{2g} (1595), e_{1u} (1485), b_{2u} (1310) and a_{1g} (992) are expected to give rise to six carbon stretching vibrations in substituted benzenes because of the removal of the degeneracy of the two components in which the two doubly degenerate vibrations split up. One remains nearly unchanged in magnitude whereas the other is slightly lowered. The vibration corresponding to the b_{2u} mode also retains its magnitude. The ring breathing frequency at 992 cm^{-1} is however very much reduced in substituted benzenes. Based on these well known considerations, the frequencies at 1300, 1302 and 1312 cm^{-1} in 2,4-, 2,5- and 2,6-dibromoanilines respectively are taken as C-C ring stretching vibrations corresponding to the b_{2u} (1310) vibration of benzene. The frequencies corresponding to the e_{1u} (1485) in benzene are located at 1450 and 1502 cm^{-1} in 2,4-; 1460 and 1515 cm^{-1} in 2,5- and 1437 and 1512 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoanilines. However the observed frequencies at 1548 and 1570 cm^{-1} in 2,4-; 1543 and 1575 cm^{-1} in 2,5- and 1535 and 1568 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoanilines correspond to the e_{2g} (1595) vibration of benzene. The ring breathing vibration corresponding to a_{1g} (992) is assigned at 830, 838 and 829 cm^{-1} in the case of these three molecules. This is in agreement with the ring breathing vibration of a large number of di-substituted compounds⁴⁻⁷.

C-Substituent Vibrations : The C-Br stretching frequencies are usually observed⁸ in the region 500-700 cm^{-1} and the frequencies at 618 and 665 cm^{-1} ; 626 and 655 cm^{-1} and 620 and 666 cm^{-1} in 2,4-, 2,5- and 2,6-dibromoanilines respectively are assigned to this mode. The C-Br in plane vibrations are assigned at 299 and 320 cm^{-1} in 2,4-, 290 and 316 cm^{-1} in 2,5- and at 299 and 312 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoanilines.

The C-NH₂ stretching vibration generally occurs in the range 1200-1300 cm^{-1} . The magnitude of this vibration in aniline⁹ and 2,6-dichloroaniline³ have been identified at 1279 and 1304 cm^{-1} respectively. In conformity with this, the moderately intense frequencies observed at 1275, 1260 and 1289 cm^{-1} in 2,4-; 2,5- and 2,6-dibromoanilines respectively have been assigned to C-NH₂ stretching mode of vibration.

$N \begin{matrix} \swarrow H \\ \searrow H \end{matrix}$ *Vibrations* : The two N-H stretching frequencies of the NH₂ group have their

magnitude in the range 3300-3500 cm^{-1} , the asymmetric stretching vibration is generally higher than the symmetric one. Evans⁹ has assigned two intense bands at 3360 and 3440

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cm^{-1} to the N-H vibration of the NH_2 group in the vibrational spectrum of aniline. The frequencies observed at 3380 and 3470 cm^{-1} in 2,4-, at 3378 and 3480 cm^{-1} in 2,5- and at 3370 and 3465 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoanilines are taken to correspond to the N-H symmetric and N-H asymmetric stretching vibrations of the NH_2 group. There is a medium strong band at 3282 cm^{-1} in 2,4-, at 3260 cm^{-1} in 2,5- and at 3280 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoanilines. This is probably the overtone of the NH_2 in-plane bending mode resonating with $\nu_s \text{NH}_2$. Such a resonating frequency has been observed at 3230 cm^{-1} in the vibrational spectrum of aniline by Evans.

The NH_2 bending or scissors mode is generally observed near $\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and accordingly the strong bands at 1620 cm^{-1} in 2,4-; 1620 cm^{-1} in 2,5- and at 1597 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dibromoanilines respectively are assigned to this mode. The other modes of vibrations are located at 700, 701 and 704 cm^{-1} (NH_2 wagging) and at 1063, 1063 and 1045 cm^{-1} (NH_2 twisting) in the 2,4-; 2,5- and 2,6-dibromoanilines respectively.

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